

THE ROLE OF DISTANCE LEARNING AND ITS EFFECTIVENESS

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ABSTRACT

People living in the current period of continuously development want to do a lot of work and achieve success in a short period of time in terms of lifestyle and work. That is why new ideas, innovations and methods are introduced almost every day in every field. Below this article will describe the implementation of the system of distance learning in education and its benefits.

Several new methods and approaches are now being introduced into the teaching process to increase the effectiveness of the teaching process and to make it easier and understandable for learners to learn.

First, we need to explain the term “distance learning”. Distance learning, form of education in which the main elements include physical separation of teachers and students during instruction and the use of various technologies to facilitate. There are the following opinions on its origin. Distance education’s origins may be traced to nineteenth century in England and continental Europe when colleges used postal services for providing education by means of correspondence (Phipps and Merisotis, 1999; Ponzurick, Russo, and Logar, 2000; Sherry, 1996; Wernet, Olliges, and Delicath, 2000).

Now it is time to apply it widely. We all know that due to the global COVID-19 pandemic, Distance Learning has been introduced in our education system. This is one of the greatest achievements in the field of education. Even so, not everyone likes it and prefers traditional learning. It is wrong to draw such a quick conclusion. Because it is impossible to reveal and understand the positive aspects of the introduced innovation in one term. A clear example of this is the academic research work of M. Shachar and Y. Neuman, published in MERLOT magazine in 2010, aimed at revealing the differences between traditional learning and distance learning. They analyzed the results of these two different teaching methods over a 20-year period to advance this meta-analysis. From this example, it can be said that any innovative method and system introduced in practice needs to be tested and analyzed over the years in order to continue in the future and fully understand its positive aspects.

The list below lists the benefits of distance learning one by one.

Saves time.

Let us focus on the average agenda of traditional learning:

- 2 hours is the time to go to and from university.
- 7 hours is the time spent in the auditorium?
- A total of 9 hours a day. Distance learning is radically different. There is a set amount of time for online conferences and the remaining assignments can be submitted at any time before the deadline. This means that there will be almost 20 hours of free time in 1 day.

Many schools, colleges, institutions and universities that provide online courses have recognized the value of reaching out to students who may otherwise be unable to participate. It could be a way to boost college graduation rates.

Study abroad - online

Another convenience is that you can study online at another foreign university without leaving your home country. The greatest opportunity that distance learning offers to students is distance learning abroad. For those who do not have the chance to go abroad, this is a great chance. In foreign educational institutions, the form of distance learning is more convenient and more cost-effective than the traditional form.

Opportunity to save money and earn money.

It is well known that in any field, the financial side is the most important and most interesting aspect. Another advantage of distance learning is low cost. Unlike textbooks in traditional learning, travel expenses and other daily expenses, Distance learning is paid only for internet service. This is equivalent to one-fourth or one-fifth of the above payments. Students are discovering that online schooling can be a cost-effective option. Although not all online classes offer reduced fees than conventional colleges, the rates associated with them can be lower.

When analyzing the time factor above, we found that students have more free time. They can use it more productively and work. It is possible to earn income through this.

Opportunity to form as an independent person.

Clearly, in distance learning, students work more on themselves. The subjects are studied independently through textbooks, Internet resources and other sources in addition to textbooks. This helps students to think independently, make decisions independently, and, in general, develop as independent individuals.

In conclusion, it should be noted that great achievements can be achieved through distance learning, especially in the study of foreign languages. Proof of this can be found in a meta-analysis entitled "Evaluating the Effectiveness of Distance Learning: A Comparison Using Meta-Analysis" co-authored by Allen, Edward Mabry, Michelle Mattrey, John Bourhis, Scott Titsworth, and Nancy Burrell : " ... for foreign language instruction, the use of distance technology demonstrated a clear superiority for that technology. Foreign language instruction in a distance environment permits the students to interact on a regular basis with native speakers of the language." (Journal of Communication, September 2004). In addition, it is important to add that all conditions and opportunities are being created for people who want to study. If the knowledge is gained with serious attention and great interest, they will undoubtedly be among the people who will come up with innovative proposals in the future. The most important thing is not to stop moving.

References:

1. D.Jaques, G. Salmon. Learning in groups. A handbook for face-to-face and online environments. 2007
2. M. Allen, E. Mabry, M. Mattrey, J. Bourhis, S. Titsworth, and N. Burrell. Evaluating the Effectiveness of Distance Learning: A Comparison Using Meta-Analysis (Journal of Communication, September 2004, pp 401-420)
3. McDaniel, et al. (2016). Classroom Discipline: Principles Old and New. Phil Delta Kappan.
4. Oyira, E. (2018). Effects of Classroom Learning Environment of Secondary School Students Attitude towards Schooling. Journal of Research in Education.
5. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9737831/>
6. <https://my.chartered.college/research-hub/distance-learning-how-effective-is-it-according-to-a-meta-analysis-of-research/>